

Artificial Intelligence in the development of educational materials: critiques, challenges, and implications for linguistic and cultural education in Brazil¹

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ABSTRACT: This article reviews the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the creation of teaching materials for Brazilian linguistic and cultural education. It aims to analyze the potential of AI in personalizing the teaching-learning process and, at the same time, discusses ethical and social challenges, such as unequal access, authorship, algorithmic biases, and the phenomenon of digital colonialism. The methodology employed was a review of the scientific literature on the subject. The analysis is based on recent critical studies that address academic integrity and authorship (Moraes & Matilha, 2023; Oliveira, 2024), the necessary pedagogical and curricular adaptations (Azambuja & Silva, 2024), and the ethical, philosophical, and social implications arising from the advancement of AI in education (Oliveira, 2023; Hirabahasi & Pilon, 2024). It is concluded that the adoption of AI requires public policies and ethical guidelines that ensure its responsible implementation, valuing cultural diversity and essential human skills.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, teaching materials, language education, ethical guidelines.

RESUMO: Este artigo revisa a aplicação da Inteligência Artificial (IA) na criação de materiais didáticos para a educação linguística e cultural brasileira. Tem como objetivo a análise do potencial da IA na personalização do processo de ensino-aprendizagem e, ao mesmo tempo, discute os desafios éticos e sociais, como desigualdade de acesso, autoria, vieses algorítmicos e o fenômeno do colonialismo digital. A metodologia empregada foi a

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revisão bibliográfica da literatura científica sobre o tema. A análise fundamenta-se em estudos críticos recentes que abordam a integridade acadêmica e autoria (Moraes & Matilha, 2023; Oliveira, 2024), as necessárias adaptações pedagógicas e curriculares (Azambuja & Silva, 2024) e as implicações éticas, filosóficas e sociais decorrentes do avanço da IA na educação (Oliveira, 2023; Hirabahasi & Pilon, 2024). Conclui-se que a adoção da IA exige políticas públicas e diretrizes éticas que garantam sua implementação responsável, valorizando a diversidade cultural e as competências humanas essenciais.

Palavras-chave: Inteligência Artificial, materiais didáticos, educação linguística, diretrizes éticas.

RESUMEN: Este artículo revisa la aplicación de la Inteligencia Artificial (IA) en la creación de materiales didácticos para la educación lingüística y cultural brasileña. Tiene como objetivo analizar el potencial de la IA en la personalización del proceso de enseñanza-aprendizaje y, al mismo tiempo, discute los desafíos éticos y sociales, como la desigualdad de acceso, la autoría, los sesgos algorítmicos y el fenómeno del colonialismo digital. La metodología empleada fue la revisión bibliográfica de la literatura científica sobre el tema. El análisis se fundamenta en estudios críticos recientes que abordan la integridad académica y la autoría (Moraes & Matilha, 2023; Oliveira, 2024), las necesarias adaptaciones pedagógicas y curriculares (Azambuja & Silva, 2024) y las implicaciones éticas, filosóficas y sociales derivadas del avance de la IA en la educación (Oliveira, 2023; Hirabahasi & Pilon, 2024). Se concluye que la adopción de la IA exige políticas públicas y directrices éticas que garanticen su implementación responsable, valorando la diversidad cultural y las competencias humanas esenciales.

Palabras clave: Inteligencia Artificial, materiales didácticos, educación lingüística, directrices éticas.

1. INTRODUCTION

The rise of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has reshaped various sectors of society, and education is no exception to this global trend. In Brazil, the discussion about the integration and impact of AI in the teaching-learning process has gained prominence, especially with regard to the development and use of teaching materials. The growing interaction with digital technologies in language courses, which includes learning through synchronous and asynchronous virtual courses, virtual exchanges such as Teletandem and Collaborative Online International Learning (COIL), in addition to the use of apps, digital dictionaries, and online

translation systems was already prompting reflections on the present and future of language education with the use of digital translators and artificial intelligence platforms (Salomão; Silva, 2023). This scenario has been significantly intensified by global events such as the COVID-19 pandemic, which has accelerated the adoption of and dependence on digital technologies in educational environments.

The complexity of this discussion ranges from the vast potential of AI to optimize educational processes and personalize learning to the ethical, social, and pedagogical challenges that its implementation poses, particularly in a country with the profound particularities and inequalities of Brazil. Brazilian literature has addressed these issues, highlighting the need to rethink pedagogical strategies, the role of critical thinking, and the importance of ethics in the face of automation and personalization of teaching (Azambuja; Silva, 2024). There are also growing concerns about the dehumanization of the educational process, data privacy and security, and the risk of digital colonialism, where dependence on private platforms and non-transparent algorithms can exacerbate inequalities and compromise digital sovereignty (Oliveira, 2023). Understanding these multiple vectors is fundamental to beginning an analysis in the Brazilian educational context.

The main objective of this article is to analyze the criticisms, challenges, and implications of Artificial Intelligence in the development of teaching materials, with a particular focus on its repercussions for linguistic and cultural education in the Brazilian context. To achieve this objective, a systematic literature review of articles published in Brazilian journals will be conducted, seeking to identify the perspectives, predominant debates, and research gaps in the national academia on the subject.

The structure of the article will follow with sections dedicated to the overview of AI applications, its criticisms and general challenges, the specific implications for the linguistic and cultural areas, culminating in a discussion on the necessary public policies and final considerations on the future of AI in Brazilian education.

2. ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHING MATERIALS

Artificial Intelligence offers transformative potential for the creation and personalization of teaching materials, allowing the learning process to adapt more effectively to each student's individual pace and style. This manifests itself in AI's ability to recommend personalized content, adjust the difficulty of exercises, and provide targeted feedback, optimizing the learning experience (Hirabahasi; Pilon, 2024). AI-assisted tools can implement automatic feedback generation and conversational agents, which can optimize the learning and assessment process (Hirabahasi; Pilon, 2024). In addition, AI can automate routine tasks for teachers, such as correcting errors, answering frequently asked questions, and assigning homework and tests, freeing up time for educators to focus on more complex and human aspects of pedagogy (Azambuja; Silva, 2024).

In the Brazilian context, the development of digital teaching materials for Portuguese language courses, such as the Grammar Awareness through Scientific Education (ConGraEduC) project, supported by the Federal Government, exemplifies the practical application of digital technologies in the development of materials aimed at improving teaching (Silva; Rottava, 2023). In this scenario, AI transcends the function of a mere automation tool to become a catalyst for pedagogical personalization and redefinition of the teaching role.

Initially, AI was perceived as a means to automate tasks and increase efficiency. However, its ability to offer personalized learning, content recommendations, and conversational agents suggests that AI is not just a substitute for repetitive tasks, but a facilitator for more adaptive and student-centered pedagogy. This evolution requires a reorientation of the teacher's focus toward higher-order human skills, such as mentoring and the development of social-emotional and critical skills. Thus, the development of AI-driven teaching materials should be conceived as a dynamic process.

able to adapt to students' individual needs. This implies that material developers need to think about flexible, modular architectures that can integrate personalization algorithms. In addition, teaching materials should be designed to complement the role of the teacher, allowing them to focus on mentoring and developing social-emotional and critical skills.

The automation provided by AI has the potential to optimize a wide range of pedagogical processes, from content management and curation to student performance assessment. AI's ability to process large volumes of data and identify complex patterns allows it to offer valuable support to both educators and students, making teaching more efficient (Moraes; Matilha, 2023). However, it is important to recognize that, despite the advantages in terms of efficiency, excessive automation raises significant concerns about the "dehumanization of the educational process," especially when applied to assessment processes, which can become impersonal and standardized (Oliveira, 2023).

The rapid evolution of AI technologies imposes on educators the need for a permanent process of "technological literacy." This means that education professionals need not only to understand the basic functioning of these tools but also to master their pedagogical application in order to fully exploit their optimization potential (Azambuja; Silva, 2024). There is an inherent tension between the pursuit of efficiency through AI automation and the risk of compromising the human and relational dimension of education. While AI can bring productivity gains and convenience, the exclusive prioritization of efficiency can erode the interpersonal and socio-emotional aspects that are intrinsic to the human learning experience.

When developing AI-powered teaching materials, it is imperative that designers and educators strike a careful balance. Materials should be designed to complement, not replace, human interaction and the development of social-emotional skills. Automation should be seen as a support to free up teachers' time for more meaningful and personalized interactions, ensuring that technology serves pedagogy and not the other way around. This requires an ethical and

reflective approach to the design of materials, ensuring that technology enhances the educational experience without compromising its human essence.

3. CRITICISMS AND CHALLENGES OF AI IN BRAZILIAN EDUCATION

The growing spread of generative language model platforms, such as ChatGPT, for example, has raised serious concerns among Brazilian educators about the phenomenon of plagiarism in education. Research points to evidence of plagiarism in the construction of responses, including literal transcriptions, paraphrases, and appropriation of ideas without proper reference to the original source (Moraes; Matilha, 2023). Critical studies indicate that Artificial Intelligence, in its current stage of development, is not capable of breaking with the "paraphrastic repetition" of what has already been said or of producing "unique meanings" that characterize genuine human authorship. AI, in this sense, only creates a "simulacrum of author function" by reproducing and recombining data to which it has access (Oliveira, 2024).

This capability of AI exacerbates the problem of plagiarism, as tools can generate texts that appear to be original and well-founded, making it difficult for teachers and evaluators to distinguish between human and machine productions. AI not only facilitates plagiarism, but also forces a redefinition of the concept of authorship and originality in education, requiring new pedagogical and evaluative approaches (Tanaka, 2024). If AI can simulate writing, the challenge goes beyond plagiarism detection; it lies in what education values as authentic intellectual production.

The pedagogical emphasis, therefore, must shift to the creative process, the critical thinking behind the text, and the student's ability to assign unique meaning. Thus, the development of teaching materials and pedagogical practices should incorporate the teaching of advanced digital literacy, including the ability to discern AI-generated texts, the ethics of using AI tools, and the appreciation of creativity and divergent thinking as irreplaceable human attributes. Assessments should be rethought

to focus on skills that AI cannot replicate, such as critical reflection, original argumentation, and the expression of a unique authorial voice.

3.1 INEQUALITY OF ACCESS, SOVEREIGNTY, AND DIGITAL COLONIALISM

The implementation of AI in education, if not carefully planned and regulated, has the potential to increase existing social and educational inequalities in Brazil. Unequal access to technology can create or deepen "digital deserts," where technological disparity widens educational gaps between different regions and social classes. The growing influence and control of the technology and innovation market by large companies, many of them foreign, can lead to a dangerous dependence on private platforms and non-transparent algorithms. This scenario is often characterized as "digital colonialism," where human productions and educational processes become increasingly mediated and controlled by external entities (Oliveira, 2023). This dependence raises questions of digital sovereignty, as educational infrastructure and systems can become hostage to commercial and geopolitical interests that do not necessarily align with the needs and values of the Brazilian context.

This means that, instead of being a tool for democratization and empowerment, AI can become a mechanism of control and subordination for countries such as Brazil, where infrastructure and technological development may not keep pace with global powers. This is not only a question of access to technology, but of sovereignty over data, educational systems, and, ultimately, the country's own educational future.

The development of AI-based teaching materials in Brazil must be guided by principles of inclusion and sovereignty. This implies promoting the development of open and free source code solutions, investing in local technological training, and educating critical citizens capable of questioning the provenance, biases, and business models of

technologies they use. Public policies should actively aim to reduce external dependence and democratize access to technology and knowledge.

3.2 ETHICS, ALGORITHMIC BIASES, AND THE VERACITY OF INFORMATION

Generative AI represents an emerging field that, in the Brazilian context, still lacks clear ethical regulations, which poses a significant challenge. Concerns include the risk of biases and prejudices embedded in algorithms, the need to moderate illegal or unethical content generated by AI, and the protection of user data privacy (Moraes; Matilha, 2023). It is important to recognize that AI, in its operation, has no intrinsic control over the veracity, ethics, or common sense of its responses. This imposes on users, including educators and students, the responsibility to analyze the information generated by AI with extreme caution and a keen critical sense, prioritizing quality and veracity.

The discussion on the use of AI in the educational context should be a collective effort, with a prominent role for higher education institutions. These institutions have the potential to address these issues critically, fostering debate and contributing to the formulation of policies and guidelines that have a social action effect (Moraes; Matilha, 2023). UNESCO, in its guidelines, already points to the need to consider AI as a means to promote "cultural and artistic education, environmental education, scientific and technological development, and early childhood care in response to the specific interests of different population groups," highlighting the importance of ethical and inclusive use (UNESCO, 2022). AI acts as an amplifier of existing social and ethical biases, requiring a proactive approach in education to deconstruct prejudices and promote information and ethical literacy. The statement that "when we say there is structural racism in AI, these patterns are not created solely by machines, but come from previously established social patterns" (Oliveira, 2023) illustrates that AI is not neutral, but reflects and can amplify biases present in training data. Education, therefore, has

a crucial role in uncovering these biases. The development of AI-based teaching materials must be accompanied by rigorous analysis to identify and mitigate algorithmic biases and prejudices. In addition, education should train students to be critical consumers of AI-generated information by teaching them to question the source, verify facts, and recognize patterns of bias and misinformation. This extends to cultural education, where AI can perpetuate stereotypes if not carefully managed, making ethical training and the development of critical thinking fundamental skills.

Table 1: Criticisms and Challenges of AI in Brazilian Education

Category	Description of the Challenge/Criticism	Implications	Relevant Sources
Academic Integrity and Authorship	Covert plagiarism and difficulty in defining/evaluating the authorship of AI-generated texts. Limitations of AI in the production of genuine originality and subjectivity.	Need to redefine evaluation methods; risk of devaluation of the process; impact on academic integrity.	MORAES & MATILHA (2023), OLIVEIRA (M. L. P. F., 2024), SILVA & ROTTAVA (2024), TANAKA (2024), VIANA & SOUZA (2024).
Pedagogical and Curricular Adaptation	The challenge of adapting teaching strategies to foster critical thinking, creativity, and ethics, rather than merely reproducing content. Limitations of AI in subjective and artistic tasks.	Outdated curricula; training of professionals with out essential skills for the AI era; loss of value of artistic and subjective expression.	AZAMBUJA & SILVA (2024), OLIVEIRA (M. L. P. F., 2024), VIANA & SOUZA (2024).
Training and Teacher Perception	Teachers' Perception of the impact of AI (threats vs. opportunities) and the urgent need for continuing education that promotes a perspective	Resistance to adopting AI; inappropriate use of technology; lack of pedagogical skills to effectively integrate AI; devaluation of the teaching profession.	OLIVEIRA (A. M., 2021), VIANA & SOUZA (2024).

	critical about technology.		
Implications Ethical, Philosophical, and Social	Risk of technological alienation, dissociation between culture, technology, and nature. Need for a critical technological thinking and addressing algorithmic biases and equity issues.	Deepening social and educational inequalities; irresponsible use of technology; loss of autonomy and critical thinking; risk of perpetuating biases.	OLIVEIRA (A. M., 2023), UNESCO (2022), HIRABAHASI & PILON (2024).
Public and Regulatory Frameworks	Absence or inadequacy of public policies and clear guidelines for the development and responsible use of AI in education, including security and promotion.	Inconsistent implementation and fragmented of AI; risks to data and user security; lack of strategic direction for the education sector.	SILVA et al. (2023), TANAKA (2024).
Technological Limitations and Challenges of Implementation	Shortage of teaching materials adapted to qualitative reasoning; limitations of AI in adhering to specific instructions (e.g., word counting) and producing varied lexical complexity.	Difficulty in the practical integration of AI in the classroom; challenges in assessing writing proficiency; underutilization of AI's potential due to lack of pedagogical infrastructure.	PEREIRA et al. (2024), SILVA & ROTTAVA (2024).

Source: Authors.

4. IMPLICATIONS FOR CULTURAL LANGUAGE EDUCATION IN BRAZIL

Artificial Intelligence has considerable potential for cultural, artistic, and heritage education, offering opportunities to analyze issues of identity, otherness, and memory. AI can be a powerful tool for the preservation and dissemination of cultural heritage. A notable example in Brazil is the project "DNA Afetivo: Kame e Kanhru" (Affective DNA: Kame and Kanhru), developed with Kaingáng indigenous schools in Rio Grande do Sul. This project involves children in the use of digital technologies

(photography, videos, graphic designs) to produce a bilingual digital game about Kaingáng social structures. The goal is to explore how emerging technologies can be assimilated and related to the preservation and perpetuation of cultural heritage, allowing the Kaingáng community to use these technologies while incorporating their own values, customs, and knowledge (Oliveira, 2023).

In addition, AI can make cultural institutions, such as museums, more attractive to visitors through interactive mediation. Computer programming with questions related to the works, which provide answers to visitors' questions, is a resource that seeks to increase engagement and visitation. AI, therefore, can be a powerful tool for cultural preservation and engagement, but only if it is integrated with local values and community participation. The example of the Kaingáng project demonstrates that technology can serve culture when conceived in a process of co-creation and when it represents diverse cultural narratives, avoiding homogenization. Cultural teaching materials developed with AI should therefore be constructed collaboratively, valuing Brazilian cultural specificity and diversity, rather than simply replicating hegemonic models.

4.1 RISKS OF CULTURAL HOMOGENIZATION AND MISINFORMATION

Despite its potential, AI also carries significant risks for cultural education, especially with regard to cultural homogenization and the proliferation of misinformation. There is a trend toward the "universalization of technologies" that can subjugate local cultures and diversity, generating a "fear of technological domination that can probabilistically predict our future behaviors and choices" (Oliveira, 2023). According to the literature, this discourse can promote the strengthening of universalizing technologies to the detriment of diverse technological and cultural practices.

The ability of AI to generate fake news and deep fakes is also a central concern, as these technologies can promote "parallel worlds" and impact

negatively influence cultural narratives and perceptions of reality (Oliveira, 2023). Furthermore, AI, with its ability to manipulate information and recognize patterns, is capable of replicating and sometimes amplifying existing social biases and patterns, including structural racism, since these patterns are not created solely by machines, but come from previously established social patterns. AI's ability to recognize patterns and generate content, while useful, carries the risk of amplifying cultural biases. This requires cultural education, when using AI, to promote in-depth critical literacy, empowering students to deconstruct algorithmic biases and recognize misinformation. Teaching materials should be designed to foster "technodiversity" and the expression of diverse cultural manifestations, rather than reinforcing stereotypes or single cultural narratives. It is essential that the implementation of AI in cultural education be accompanied by continuous reflection on how technology can serve to enhance Brazilian cultural plurality, without falling into the trap of standardization or informational distortion.

5. PUBLIC POLICIES AND ETHICAL GUIDELINES

Generative AI represents an emerging field that, in the Brazilian context, still lacks clear ethical regulations, which constitutes a significant challenge. The absence of a robust legal and ethical framework allows issues such as biases and prejudices incorporated into algorithms, the need to moderate illegal or unethical content generated by AI, and the protection of user data privacy to remain without clear guidelines (Moraes; Matilha, 2023).

The discussion on the direction and conduct of AI should be a collective effort, with a prominent role for higher education institutions. These institutions have the potential to address these issues critically, fostering debate and contributing to the formulation of policies and guidelines that have a social action effect (Moraes; Matilha, 2023). An analysis of public policies for the development of AI in Brazil points to the need for reflection on the creation and implementation of these

policies in the face of exponential technological development, the possibilities for innovation, and the safety of users and systems (Silva et al., 2023). The ethical implementation of AI in education is not merely a technical challenge, but a social issue. The absence of clear regulation can lead to a scenario where technological innovation advances without considering its broader social and ethical implications. Thus, public policies must be proactive, discussed in a network of partnerships with different actors, and seek a balance between fostering innovation and ensuring equity, privacy, and human values.

5.1 TEACHER TRAINING AND SKILLS DEVELOPMENT FOR THE AI ERA

The rapid evolution of AI technologies requires educators to undergo a continuous process of technological literacy. However, this training must go beyond the instrumental mastery of tools. The role of the teacher is changing, with an increasing focus on the development of interpersonal, emotional, ethical, and critical thinking skills in students. The literature indicates that certain skills will continue to be taught by human teachers, including the development of interpersonal skills, emotional skills, leadership, ethical attitudes, aesthetic sense, decision-making ability, understanding of reality, and research skills (Oliveira, 2021).

Research on Brazilian teachers' perceptions of AI reveals that, although they recognize the impact of AI on changing the skill profile of the profession, they see technology as a developer of human skills, not just a threat. Humanities teachers, for example, show greater sensitivity to the sociocultural impacts of AI. Flexibility and adaptability, supported by cross-cutting skills, are perceived as central to facing future challenges, aligning with studies on mixed human teams and AI systems (Oliveira, 2021). The effective integration of AI requires a paradigm shift in

teacher training, moving beyond proficiency in tools to foster critical pedagogical agency. This implies redefining the training curriculum, emphasizing essential human skills and promoting the role of the teacher as a mentor, critical thinker, and consultant who ensures that AI serves humanity. Training should enable educators to guide students in navigating an AI-mediated world, developing their capacity for discernment, creativity, and ethical responsibility.

6. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Artificial Intelligence in the development of teaching materials in the Brazilian context presents a scenario of vast potential and complex challenges. On the one hand, AI offers unprecedented opportunities for personalizing teaching, adapting to the individual needs of students and optimizing pedagogical processes, freeing educators to focus on more humanistic aspects of learning. This ability of AI to act as a catalyst for a more adaptive and student-centered pedagogy represents a redefinition of the teaching role, which shifts from content transmission to mentoring and the development of socio-emotional and critical skills.

On the other hand, the literature review reveals substantial criticisms and urgent challenges. AI raises profound questions about authorship and originality, with the phenomenon of plagiarism becoming more complex due to AI's ability to generate texts that simulate human production. This requires a redefinition of what education values as authentic intellectual production, focusing on the creative process and critical thinking. In addition, the implementation of AI in Brazil faces the risk of exacerbating inequalities in access, creating digital deserts and perpetuating digital colonialism where dependence on private platforms and non-transparent algorithms can compromise educational and cultural sovereignty. The threat of dehumanization of the educational process through excessive automation, especially in assessments, paradoxically reinforces the

need to reevaluate the humanistic purpose of education, focusing on the development of intellectual and moral virtues and social-emotional skills. Finally, AI, by amplifying social and ethical biases present in training data, requires a proactive approach in education to deconstruct prejudices and promote information and ethical literacy.

For language education, AI acts as a bridge between theory and practice, but the challenge lies in capturing the sociocultural nuances of language, requiring teaching materials to complement formal education with the development of intercultural communicative competence. In textual production, AI's "simulacrum of authorship" imposes a shift in focus to the creative process and the student's unique authorial voice. For cultural education, AI can be a powerful tool for preservation and engagement, as demonstrated by projects that integrate technology and indigenous culture. However, the risk of cultural homogenization and the proliferation of misinformation require that AI be used to foster technodiversity and the expression of multiple cultural manifestations, rather than to reinforce stereotypes.

In summary, the implementation of Artificial Intelligence in Brazilian education is not merely a technical issue, but a social issue that requires robust public policies and ethical guidelines. It is important that there be a collective effort to regulate the use of AI, ensuring that technological innovation is balanced with equity, privacy, and human values. Teacher training should consider the development of mentoring and facilitation skills, focusing on the development of essential human competencies that AI cannot replicate. Only with a critical, ethical, and inclusive approach will it be possible to harness the transformative potential of AI to build an educational future in Brazil that values human development and the country's rich linguistic and cultural diversity.

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